

Commercializing Low-Earth Orbit and the Role of the International Space Station

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Abstract— With the extension of the International Space Station (ISS) operations until at least 2024, NASA and its partners have the opportunity to leverage the orbiting laboratory to conduct research and validate systems in microgravity that will better prepare humans and systems for future missions, farther into deep space. Beyond 2024, it is vitally important to ensure that the infrastructure and capabilities that have been developed over the past three decades in low Earth orbit (LEO) do not languish, and in fact are used to enable sustainable commercial activity in LEO beyond the ISS.

This paper will explore the opportunities and challenges in developing the commercial market in LEO through the ISS program while at the same time continuing to use the ISS as a testbed to enable human missions into deep space.. System and technology capability gaps requiring demonstrations on the ISS will be discussed in detail. NASA's strategic plan for leveraging the ISS to enable commercial markets and stimulate

commercial supply of LEO services will be summarized, along with initial steps and progress. The intersection between NASA's needs beyond LEO and commercial LEO platforms will be explored. Finally, the paper will discuss preliminary measures that will indicate when a transition from ISS to the Proving Ground is appropriate.

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The Small Satellite Orbital Deployer is seen in action on September 17, 2015.

1. INTRODUCTION

The International Space Station has reached a pivotal time. With its assembly complete as of 2011, the focus has shifted toward utilizing the massive on-orbit laboratory to the greatest extent possible. Permanently crewed with six international astronauts and cosmonauts, the U.S. and its international partners have nearly filled the internal and external volume and all of the available crew time with groundbreaking research and technology payloads. To further this commitment, the U.S., Russian, Japanese, and Canadian space agencies have committed to supporting the ISS until at least 2024 [1], and the European Space Agency is moving toward the same commitment.

Today, NASA is the primary driver for both the supply and demand for human spaceflight in LEO. It is NASA's goal to transition its activities from LEO to the cis-lunar Proving Ground and enable commercial industry to take over the supply of capabilities and services to LEO based on a sustainable private market demand begun through the ISS. As NASA plans for this transition, it is crucial that we focus the remaining ISS mission on two critical goals: enabling future deep space missions beyond low Earth orbit, and enabling sustainable commercial markets in low Earth orbit. Although these goals may seem disparate, they in fact are very closely related in NASA's human spaceflight strategy.

2. THE ISS'S ROLE IN ENABLING SUSTAINED HUMAN SPACEFLIGHT

NASA's strategy for enabling sustained human spaceflight beyond low Earth orbit begins with the ISS, and cannot succeed without the ISS. Figure 1 depicts the major technology, human health, and operational challenge areas that need to be solved for human missions to deep space, including Mars. The items shaded green represent capability gaps that can be fully closed using the ISS, and items shaded in yellow can be at least partially closed using the ISS. Areas that align with the National Research Council's top technical challenges are designated with an asterisk [2]. In order to prepare for human expeditions into deep space, we must first use the unique environment of ISS to conduct the research and technology demonstrations necessary to keep our crews safe and productive on long duration spaceflights. The ISS –which has been home to a continuous human presence on orbit for 15 years – is NASA's only long-duration flight analog for future human deep-space missions, and it provides an invaluable laboratory for research with direct application to the exploration requirements that address human risks associated with deep-space missions. It is also the perfect technology testbed for validating long-duration habitation systems such as life support, environmental monitoring, spacesuits, and crew medical and exercise equipment. Deep space missions will also require crews to operate with greater autonomy and with communications delays. Robots will share crew tasks and perform station-keeping tasks during crew-tended

spacecraft periods. The ISS is an ideal place to practice these techniques.

Current Planning and Progress

In order to determine what specific capability gaps require the ISS as a platform, NASA has established agency-wide System Maturation Teams (SMT's) in each discipline area. These teams have identified the capability gaps between the current state of the art and what will be required to execute deep space missions including Mars transit and surface missions, and the activities required to close those gaps. Gap-closing activities may include ground testing and in-space demonstrations on the ISS or other platforms in the Proving Ground. The ISS-specific gap-closing activities include demonstrations in the following areas:

- Highly reliable and more closed-loop Life Support Systems
- Environmental Monitoring that does not rely on sample return to Earth
- Fire Safety and Response systems that work across multiple architecture elements and environments
- EVA Systems for microgravity and surface use
- Crew Health and Performance capabilities including exercise equipment, medical diagnostic and treatment equipment, and long-duration food storage and nutrition
- Thermal and Cryogenic Fluid systems for variable deep space and planetary environments
- Efficient Power and Energy Storage Systems including advanced solar arrays
- Communication and Navigation Systems for deep space
- Lightweight Structures and Materials, including in-space manufacturing
- Radiation Monitoring and Shielding techniques
- Autonomous Operations
- Automated Rendezvous and Docking
- Robotics, including human assist and free flyer robots
- Entry, descent, and landing technologies
- In-situ resource utilization techniques and tools in microgravity

Plans for ISS demonstrations for each of these areas span between now and the mid-2020's, but are highly funding-dependent. That being said, progress in a number of these areas is already being made. Figure 2 is a pictorial representation of just some of the current ISS technology demonstrations. In addition, the ISS international partners are engaged in supporting the SMT's with their own gap-filling technology contributions and plans.

ISS can close these gaps for future missions

Figure 1. Future mission gaps that can be closed using the International Space Station

Figure 2. Examples of current ISS Technology Demonstrations for future missions

3. ENABLING THE COMMERCIALIZATION OF LEO

The Groundwork Already Laid

Since the shift from assembly to utilization, the ISS program has evolved to a more customer-focused, research-enabling on-orbit laboratory. With the NASA Authorization Act of 2010 [3], the ISS National Lab was created to allow broader use of the ISS by the private sector and non-NASA government agencies. 50% of the available crew time, upmass, and rack space has been allocated to the National Lab, and the Center for Advancement of Science in Space (CASIS) was established as the non-profit organization to populate and manage these resources. Through a strategy of outreach and education regarding the benefits of microgravity with a broad variety of industry sectors, as of 2015 CASIS has filled its 50% share of ISS resources with a healthy pipeline of commercial and Other Government Agency research and technology payloads. Figure 3 demonstrates the variety of private sector business that CASIS has attracted to the ISS National Lab. An extremely promising trend is that more than 75% of the commercial projects that came through CASIS in 2015 required zero funding from CASIS and only received the subsidized infrastructure cost for upmass/downmass/crew time.

Figure 3. Examples of commercial companies working with CASIS to perform research on ISS

Supporting this pipeline, the ISS is serviced by a fleet of operational vehicles, including two U.S. cargo resupply vehicles: Space Exploration Technologies' (SpaceX) Dragon and Orbital ATK's Cygnus. The cargo flights have demonstrated the viability of the Government use of commercially-provided services for the delivery of experiments, supplies, and spares to the Station, enabling NASA to focus its development efforts on deep-space vehicles to take our astronauts beyond LEO. These U.S. commercial space transportation capabilities were enabled under a partnership that leveraged NASA and private industry investments [4]. NASA has recently announced the award of follow-on cargo resupply services contracts, known as CRS-2, that will perform cargo resupply missions beginning as early as 2018 and continuing through 2024. These will include the two incumbent providers, SpaceX and Orbital ATK, as well as new provider Sierra Nevada Corporation with their Dreamchaser vehicle [5].

Following in the footsteps of the Commercial Cargo program, in 2014 NASA contracted with two U.S providers for crew transportation and rescue services for ISS. The Commercial Crew Transportation Capability contracts will complete the development of domestic systems to provide safe, reliable, cost-effective access to and from ISS. SpaceX's Crew Dragon and Boeing's CST-100 spacecraft will begin ferrying our crews to the Station from U.S. soil by 2018.

With the commercial cargo and crew transportation, and National Lab groundwork laid, NASA has begun to focus on its next steps to further enable commercial markets in LEO.

The Vision

In 2014, NASA began development of a strategic plan for enabling LEO commercialization. Informed by feedback from a Request for Information and a subsequent workshop with industry stakeholders, NASA established the Vision and Goals as shown in Figure 4.

Vision: Sustained economic activity in LEO enabled by human spaceflight, driven by private and public investments creating value and benefitting Earth through commercial supply and public and private demand

Figure 4. ISS LEO Commercialization Strategic Plan Overview

Initial Progress and Next Steps

Specific objectives and activities for each goal have been developed and progress is already being made in several areas:

Goal 1: “LEO commercialization enabled by leveraging ISS.”— To leverage the ISS, the Revolutionize ISS for Science and Exploration (RISE) initiative has been undertaken to implement process improvements to streamline the customer experience in flying payloads to the ISS. The RISE motto is “making the right thing to do the easiest thing to do.” For example, superfluous requirements that Payloads are required to meet and verify have been reduced by nearly 50%. The ISS Program also continues to explore more commercial friendly acquisition strategies, and opportunities to transition payload integration and operations work from NASA to one or more commercial partners.

Goal 2: “The policy and regulatory environment promotes commercialization of LEO.” — To foster a more commercial LEO policy and regulatory environment, NASA is beginning to reach out and leverage current interagency working groups to engage with other stakeholder

government agencies to address policy and regulatory concerns that have been raised by the private sector, as well as strategize about additional incentives and initiatives that can help to stimulate demand for commercial LEO activities.

Goal 3: “A robust, self-sustaining, and cost effective supply of US commercial services to/in/from LEO accommodates public and private demands.” — To stimulate a cost effective supply of commercial LEO services, NASA plans to leverage its acquisition of future deep space habitation capabilities to enable LEO-similar capabilities that can transition to commercial LEO platforms. Figure 5 shows a conceptual intersection between NASA’s habitation capability gaps for future deep space missions with potential human-tended or permanently crewed commercial LEO platform habitation capability needs. As an example, LEO-only platforms may rely more on expendable-based life support systems, while a deep space Hab will be driven to more closed-loop life support architectures. However, both will require highly reliable life support systems so that crew time and cost of spare parts to maintain the systems are minimized. NASA plans to refine these potential areas of “intersection” through interactions with the commercial

space industry. Through a range of commercial-friendly acquisition strategies for acquiring its deep space capabilities, NASA believes that private industry can be positioned to supply some of these same capabilities to enable commercial platforms in LEO beyond the ISS. Activities have already begun with the award of multiple Habitation and Habitation Systems-related Broad Agency Announcement contracts by NASA in 2015 [6]. These studies, along with other planned touch points with industry, will help NASA gauge the areas of commercial interest that can potentially be leveraged. In addition, NASA continues to look for opportunities to transition from NASA-supplied services on the ISS to commercially supplied services.

space, and will eventually move to the vicinity of Mars before settling on the Martian surface. It is essential that the journey does not create a gap in human spaceflight. We do not want to transition from the ISS before we are flying human missions to cis-lunar space, nor do we want to transition from the ISS before we have used it to demonstrate the critical deep space habitation capabilities, including mitigating the human health and performance risks associated with long duration missions, we will need for this journey. A smooth transition from ISS to deep space habitation will look more like a series of completed indicators than a specific end date; if human missions into cis-lunar space are underway, if the key technologies for deep space exploration are at a high readiness level, and if there is a demonstrable and sustainable demand for commercial LEO platforms in place, the ISS mission is likely at an appropriate transition point.

As described in this paper, NASA’s human spaceflight strategy for the ISS and beyond into the Proving Ground is aligned with two key goals: enabling NASA’s beyond-LEO habitation capabilities while leveraging those capabilities for the supply of commercial LEO platforms; and stimulating LEO demand and markets that will be able to be sustained by the commercial sector. Through execution of the strategic plan developed around these goals, a smooth transition of continuous human presence in space from the ISS to the Proving Ground and on to Mars is achievable.

Figure 5. Cross-section of LEO and Deep Space Habitation Capabilities

Goal 4: “Broad sectors of the economy using LEO for commercial purposes.” — To stimulate demand for sustained, market-enabling LEO commercial activities, NASA and CASIS have targeted three initial focus areas believed to have the potential for success: protein crystallization, organ bioengineering, and on-orbit production (such as exotic fibers or other materials). These areas vary in level of current development, and thus will require different approaches including forming or joining existing consortia, determining how to enable ISS research and demonstrations in these areas, and follow through to implementation and development of resulting markets. NASA and CASIS are also engaging other government agencies with interest in these initiatives, as multiple stakeholders and supporters are essential for successful creation of sustainable ongoing LEO commercial activities. Identifying and transitioning primary sponsorship for these enabling research and market areas to other government agency stakeholders will enable NASA to focus on its human spaceflight exploration mission beyond LEO.

4. SUMMARY

Continuity of human spaceflight is essential to NASA’s goal to expand human presence into the solar system and to the surface of Mars. NASA’s Journey to Mars begins with the ISS and continues into the Proving Ground in cis-lunar

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BIOGRAPHY

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Monitoring Systems. Ms. Gatens has 30 years of experience at NASA in development and management of Environmental Control and Life Support Systems for the International Space Station and Orion programs, and in the ISS Program. Ms. Gatens held various leadership positions at the NASA Marshall Space Flight Center and served as Manager for the Orion Crew Support and Thermal Systems before transferring to NASA Headquarters in 2012. Prior to being selected as Deputy Director, Ms. Gatens served as the Systems and Technology Demonstration Manager for the ISS Division, focusing agency efforts to utilize the ISS as a testbed to mature technologies needed for future missions. Ms. Gatens holds a Bachelor of Chemical Engineering degree from the Georgia Institute of Technology.